

Appendix 2. Search submission and peer review assessment based on Press checklist

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/06/30

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure.

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?.

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Healthy people OR People with high blood pressure
- I** GABA
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

降圧剤を使うと 2020369297 などが含まれる *reviewer アドバイスにより検索後追加。 血圧降下作用, 抗高血圧, 降圧作用

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 @"Gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"/TH [4,893 件]
#2 "ガンマ-アミノ酪酸"/TA or "4-Aminobutanoic Acid"/TA or "γ-Amino Butyric Acid"/TA or ガンマアミノ酪酸/TA or ガンマロン/TA or "ギャバ"/TA or "γ-Aminobutyric Acid"/TA or "γ-アミノブチル酸"/TA or "γ-アミノ酪酸"/TA or "γアミノ酪酸"/TA or "gamma Aminobutyric Acid"/TA or "Gammalon"/TA or "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"/TA or "GABA"/TA or "Aminalon"/TA or "アミナロン"/TA [7,926 件]
#3 #1 or #2 [9,113 件]
#4 [血圧]/TH [46,203 件]

#5 [降圧剤]/TH [87,036 件]

#6 "Blutdruck"/TA or "Blood Pressure"/TA or "Diastolic Pressure"/TA or "Mean Blood Pressure"/TA or "Systolic Pressure"/TA or 血圧 /TA or 血圧降下作用/TA or 抗高血圧/TA or 降圧作用/TA [201,911 件]

#7 #4 or #5 or #6 [273,657 件]

#8 #3 and #7 [317 件]

#9 (#8) and (PT=会議録除く) [190 件]

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/6

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

降圧剤/TH ご検討ありがとうございます。確認しました。

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/06/29

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

MEDLINE

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

PubMed

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"[Mesh:NoExp]  40,352
2      "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR Aminoaloon*[Title/Abstract] OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR "4-
Aminobutyric Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR Gammalon[Title/Abstract] OR GABA[tiab] OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR "γ-
Aminobutyric Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR"Gammalon"[Title/Abstract] OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"[Title/Abstract:-0]
69,437
3      #1 OR #2          81,799
4      "Blood Pressure"[mh]  308,955

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5	"Blutdruck"[tiab] or "Blood Pressure"[tiab] or "Diastolic Pressure"[tiab] or "Mean Blood Pressure"[tiab] or "Systolic Pressure"[tiab]	364,652
6	Antihypertensive Agents[mh]	69,460
7	antihypertensive*[tiab]	60,658
8	#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7	560,106
9	#3 AND #8	1,365
10	("Animals"[MeSH] NOT (Animals[MeSH] AND "Humans"[MeSH]))	5,132,560
11	#9 NOT #10	383

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/7

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Antihypertensive Agents/TH (降圧剤) ご検討ありがとうございます。確認しました。

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

#2 Gammalon[Title/Abstract]が重複しているようです。

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

検索式は網羅性の点から十分かと思います。#2 *Gammalon*[Title/Abstract]の重複分を削除してはいかがでしょうか。

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/02

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Wiley)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	MeSH descriptor: [gamma-Aminobutyric Acid] this term only in Cochrane Reviews	31
2	("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminoalcol* OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "gamma-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	42
3	#1 OR #2 in Cochrane Reviews	42
4	MeSH descriptor: [Blood Pressure] explode all trees in Cochrane Reviews	89
5	MeSH descriptor: [Antihypertensive Agents] explode all trees in Cochrane Reviews	92
6	("Blutdruck" or "Blood Pressure" or "Diastolic Pressure" or "Mean Blood Pressure" or "Systolic Pressure"):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	582

7	(antihypertensive*):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	117
8	#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 in Cochrane Reviews	601
9	#3 AND #8 in Cochrane Reviews	2

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/7

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/02

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Wiley)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      MeSH descriptor: [gamma-Aminobutyric Acid] this term only i in Trials      1393
2      ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminalon* OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR
GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid"):ti,ab,kw in Trials      3487
3      #1 OR #2 in Trials      3487
4      MeSH descriptor: [Blood Pressure] explode all trees in Trials      33808
5      MeSH descriptor: [Antihypertensive Agents] explode all trees in Trials      9534
6      ("Blutdruck" or "Blood Pressure" or "Diastolic Pressure" or "Mean Blood Pressure" or "Systolic Pressure"):ti,ab,kw in Trials
109916

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7	(antihypertensive*):ti,ab,kw in Trials	21878
8	#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 in Trials	116556
9	#3 AND #8 in Trials	187

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/7

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/03

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

CINAHL with Full Text

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

// S5 の"Blood Pressure Alteration (Saba CCC)"は現時点(7/3)の検索では影響はなさそうでしたが、解説のページに” For citations that concern the general topic or topics related to the term, consider searching the subject heading: BLOOD PRESSURE. ” と記載があったので追加しました。(この是非についてご確認お願いします)

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

S1      (MH "GABA") Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      2,648
S2      TI ( "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminoal* OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR
GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid" OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" ) OR AB ( "gamma-
Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminoal* OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino
Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid" OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" ) Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects
Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      3,106

```


S3	(S1 OR S2) Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	4,791
S4	(MH "Antihypertensive Agents") Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	15,948
S5	(MH "Blood Pressure+") OR (MH "Blood Pressure Alteration (Saba CCC)") Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	56,560
S6	TI ("Blutdruck" or "Blood Pressure" or "Diastolic Pressure" or "Mean Blood Pressure" or "Systolic Pressure" OR TI antihypertensive*) OR AB ("Blutdruck" or "Blood Pressure" or "Diastolic Pressure" or "Mean Blood Pressure" or "Systolic Pressure" OR antihypertensive*) Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	89,161
S7	S4 OR S5 OR S6 Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	118,519
S8	(S3 AND S7) Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	81

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/07/08

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

S5 の"Blood Pressure Alteration (Saba CCC)"、scope note を読むと血圧の変化のことかと思うので、入れて OK だと思います。

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

strategy の変更ではなく、以下の記載についてご確認をお願いします。
S6 TI ("Blutdruck" or ~ OR TI antihypertensive*)のようにカッコ内にさらに TI が入ることで件数が減っているようです。
最終検索結果 S8 の件数には影響がないようですが、AB のカッコ内と統一してはいかがでしょうか。

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
---------	--------------	-----------------------	----------------------

1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

S6 の記載のご確認をお願いします。

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/20

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

African Index Medicus, Index Medicus for the Eastern Mediterranean Region, Index Medicus for the South-East Asia Region, Latin America and the Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences, Western Pacific Region Index Medicus

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

(tw:("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR aminalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR gammalon OR gaba OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid" OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid") OR (mh:("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"))) AND (tw:("Blutdruck" or "Blood Pressure" or "Diastolic Pressure" or "Mean Blood Pressure" or "Systolic Pressure" OR antihypertensive*) OR (mh:("Blood Pressure" OR "Antihypertensive Agents"))) 54*

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/07/20

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

検索語が網羅されていることを確認しました。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/04

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform(ICTRP)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

トップページの簡易検索の場合どのフィールドを参照して検索した結果なのかが不明なため、検索式には含めていません。(247 records for 223 trials found) と表示され、ヒットした内容を確認するとノイズが多い印象です。(ICTRP には問い合わせ済み)

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1 in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") 153 records for 152 trials found!

2 in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") 90 records for 78 trials found

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/6

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Title と intervention の検索、確認しました。

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/04

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

PROSPERO

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

履歴の組み合わせ機能なし

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	MeSH DESCRIPTOR gamma-Aminobutyric Acid EXPLODE ALL TREES	67
2	"gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	46 //""フレーズなしでも 46
3	Aminalol 1	
4	"4-Aminobutanoic Acid"	0 //""フレーズなしでも 0
5	"4-Aminobutyric Acid"	2
6	Gammalon 0	
7	GABA 180	
8	"γ-Amino Butyric Acid"	0

9 "γ-Aminobutyric Acid" 0
10 "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" 0

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/6

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested

C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

確認：フリーターム検索を合わせると 192 件になるようです。

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/03

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov (classic)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

ここは *Antihypertensive Agents* を入れると薬そのものが I や E に設定されている試験になっていたので 血圧関連のみの KW にしています
新バージョンとの検索結果の差分が出ていたので確認しながら進める (I と O を other term フィールドで掛け合わせ t

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("Blood Pressure")	265
2	Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("arterial pressures")	265

- 3 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("Blutdruck") 0
- 4 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("Diastolic Pressure") 69
- 5 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("Mean Blood Pressure") 43
- 6 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("Systolic Pressure") 73

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

KWは網羅されていると思います。
旧サイトの方が、トータルの件数がわずかに多いでしょうか。

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/04

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on blood pressure

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

UMIN-CTR

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect blood pressure?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Blood pressure
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

履歴の組み合わせ機能なし
Multi line searchは無効?無関係なデータがヒットしてきたので *single line search* で実施
 検索ガイドはないためフリーワード検索・検索の画面の様子が不明 (フリーワード検索でカバーしている印象だが念のため検索画面の目的1 を使って同じ検索を実行した)

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	フリーワード検索 : 検索キーワード "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	0	/" フレーズなしでも 0
2	フリーワード検索 : 検索キーワード Aminalton	0	
3	フリーワード検索 : 検索キーワード "4-Aminobutanoic Acid"	0	
4	フリーワード検索 : 検索キーワード "4-Aminobutyric Acid"	0	

5	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Gammalon	0
6	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "γ-Amino Butyric Acid"	0
7	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "γ-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
8	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
9	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ガンマ-アミノ酪酸	0
10	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ガンマアミノ酪酸	0
11	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ガンマロン	0
12	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ギャバ	3
13	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード γ-アミノブチル酸	0
14	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード γ-アミノ酪酸	22
15	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード γアミノ酪酸	0
16	検索：目的1 "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	0 //16-23 は本番では省略もありかと考えます (ご意見お願いします)
17	検索：目的1 Aminalon	0
18	検索：目的1 "4-Aminobutanoic Acid"	0
19	検索：目的1 "4-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
20	検索：目的1 Gammalon	0
21	検索：目的1 "γ-Amino Butyric Acid"	0
22	検索：目的1 "γ-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
23	検索：目的1 "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
24	検索：目的1 ガンマ-アミノ酪酸	0
25	検索：目的1 ガンマアミノ酪酸	0
26	検索：目的1 ガンマロン	0
27	検索：目的1 ギャバ	0
28	検索：目的1 γ-アミノブチル酸	0
29	検索：目的1 γ-アミノ酪酸	2
30	検索：目的1 γアミノ酪酸	0

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

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5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

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Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

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Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

フリーワード検索のみでよいように思います。
目的での検索の検証、ありがとうございます。
時間が経ってしまい大変恐縮ですが7/5に1件追加されたようで、全体で26件になるでしょうか。